

Ordered GaAs quantum dots by droplet epitaxy using in-situ direct laser interference patterning.

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ABSTRACT: We report the fabrication of highly ordered arrays of GaAs/AlGaAs quantum dots (QDs) by droplet epitaxy using in-situ direct laser interference patterning (DLIP). Two-dimensional arrays of Ga droplets with a periodicity of ~ 300 nm are initially formed on nanoisland structured AlGaAs surfaces due to the localised surface diffusion under the influence of a thermal gradient imposed by the light pulse. After crystallisation under an arsenic flux, precisely ordered arrays of GaAs single dots are obtained. The size distribution and optical properties of the ordered GaAs QDs are shown to be optimised by careful choice of parameters for nucleation and droplet formation.

Self-assembled quantum dots (QDs) have attracted tremendous interest, not only for their basic physical properties but also for potential applications in advanced optical and electronic devices.¹⁻³ Amongst the techniques to produce QDs, droplet epitaxy (DE)^{4,5} is an emerging and powerful alternative methodology with some advantages compared with the commonly used Stranski-Krastanov (SK) approach⁶. In the DE approach, group III metallic clusters are deposited on a single-crystalline semiconductor surface without initially supplying group V atoms. Droplet nucleation then proceeds due to surface tension, which allows for the self-assembly of strain-free material combinations. This leads to further advantages, for example, nearly pure GaAs QDs with AlGaAs barriers can be formed⁷, whereas In(Ga)As/GaAs QDs grown by the SK method suffer from elemental intermixing.

The random positioning and local variation in density of conventional randomly self-organized QDs present a severe problem for reproducible nanophotonic device fabrication. To address this, many research works have been carried out on the fabrication of site-controlled QDs with the aim to produce highly aligned III-V semiconductor nanostructures by lithography, etch and regrowth. The methods include using electron-beam lithography, nano-imprint lithography, or tip-assisted patterning.⁸⁻¹⁰ However, the main problem related to pattern and regrowth is the introduction of contaminants and defects at the regrown interface caused by chemical and physical processes which relate to the ex-situ transfer of the pattern to the wafer.¹¹ In order to fabricate ordered QDs with high quality, it is important to produce defect- and contaminant-free QDs with well-controlled positioning. To address this, there have been reports on the use of direct laser interference patterning (DLIP) to assist the SK growth of In(Ga)As QD arrays.¹²⁻¹⁵ We have recently reported the use of this technique to produce high quality In(Ga)As QD arrays

and have described the underlying mechanism in terms of surface diffusion under the influence of a thermal gradient generated from the light pattern.^{14,15} The technique offers a rapid, non-invasive and large-area nanostructuring method. However, the growth of patterned QDs by DE method using DLIP has not yet been reported.

In this paper, we have investigated the growth, structural, and optical properties of GaAs QD arrays formed in situ using a DLIP patterning process which induces the ordering of gallium droplets. The samples were characterised by atomic force microscopy (AFM) using an FSM NanoView-1000 instrument and by photoluminescence (PL) measurements.

The samples used in this work were grown by Molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), which is equipped with symmetric optical viewports that allow four laser beams to converge on the growing wafer. The details of the optical setup and laser conditions for DLIP were discussed in Ref 16. A 300 nm thick GaAs buffer layer and a 100 nm thick Al_{0.3}Ga_{0.7}As layer were successively grown on semi-insulating GaAs (100) substrates at a substrate temperature (T_s) of 630 °C. For the formation of Ga droplets with a low density on AlGaAs surface, the T_s was cooled to 100 °C, the arsenic valve was closed and the arsenic pressure inside the chamber decreased below 3×10^{-10} mbar. The AlGaAs surface showed a $c(4 \times 4)$ reconstruction at a T_s below 500 °C, which was confirmed by the reflection of high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED) patterns. Before the formation of Ga droplets, a four-beam single pulse DLIP process was performed using a single 7 ns pulse of 355 nm light from a flash-lamp pumped laser (Innolas Spotlight). Our optical arrangement produces an approximately 5 mm diameter beam overlap on the sample containing a square interference array of 300 nm pitch, which depends on the wavelength of the laser and the angle of incidence.

After a growth interruption of 20 seconds, 2.0 monolayers (MLs) of Ga were deposited to form Ga droplets at a growth rate of 0.25 ML/s. The droplets were subsequently crystallised into GaAs islands under an As_4 flux of 2.4×10^{-4} mbar at $T_s = 200$ °C for 5 min. After the crystallization, spotty RHEED patterns were observed, indicating that the droplets had crystallised into three-dimensional nanostructures. The surface morphologies of the resulting GaAs QDs were then investigated ex-situ by AFM.

Figure 1(a) illustrates an AFM image of shallow nanoisland arrays on an AlGaAs surface formed after DLIP with a laser irradiation energy of ~ 16 mJ. These nanoislands are formed with a period of ~ 300 nm which is set by the interference geometry and laser wavelength. The average height (h) and width (D) of these circular islands are ~ 1 and 100 nm, respectively. Small dips of 2-3 ML are formed at the boundary around the islands. Figure 1(b) shows an AFM image of 2.0 ML GaAs QDs formed on the nanoisland structured surface, in which 1-3 dots are nucleated at the edge of the nanoislands. These QDs present a bimodal size distribution. The larger QDs are typically ~ 6 nm in h and 70 nm in D while the smaller QDs are h of 5 nm and D of 40 nm. The formation of larger dots results from the coalescence of smaller QDs. The growth mechanism can be qualitatively explained by the following. During the DLIP process, adatoms on the AlGaAs surface undergo surface migration driven by the interference-induced thermal gradients which consequently form periodic nanoislands at the interference minima. When supplying a Ga molecular beam on the surface, the Ga adatoms are sufficiently mobile to migrate towards the edge of nanoislands driven by the gradient of chemical potential¹⁷ towards the shallow dips of the island edge where they nucleate to form metallic droplets. The Ga droplets then crystallise into GaAs QDs under subsequent As_4 supply. The growth mechanism is very similar to our previously reported results of InAs QDs on GaAs surfaces by DLIP.^{14,15} The number of QDs per site is controlled by the nanoisland size which is related to the laser energy.¹⁵ When the size of islands is large

FIG. 1. AFM images showing (a) an array of nanoislands on AlGaAs surface before the formation of Ga droplets and (b) the nucleation of 2.0 ML GaAs QDs at the edge of small nanoislands under a laser irradiation energy ~ 16 mJ.

enough to allow for the nucleation of several droplets at the island edge, multiple QDs with a bimodal distribution can be formed as shown in Fig. 1(b). To achieve a single dot per site therefore requires control of the island size, amongst other secondary factors.

Figures 2(a) and (b) show AFM images of an array of single Ga droplets and single GaAs QDs under a lower energy laser irradiation (~ 12 mJ). Well-ordered single Ga droplets are formed which crystallise into GaAs QDs with the same period (~ 300 nm). A well-aligned array of single dots is formed (density $\sim 8 \times 10^8$ cm⁻²). In Fig. 2 (c), we show that the height (h) and width (D) of the Ga droplets orientations are approximately 4 and 40 nm and the patterned Ga droplets have a symmetrical structure in contrast to observations of In(Ga)As QDs.¹⁴ Fig. 2 (d) shows ordered QDs following crystallisation under arsenic with similar dimensions to that of the droplets. These dimensions are very similar to that of smaller QDs in Fig. 1(b). There is also a considerable reduction in the surface roughness, which presumably comes from surface annealing during the arsenic exposure. The results indicate that when sufficiently small nanoislands are formed using lower laser pulse energies, the nucleation area becomes small enough to prevent multiple droplets from forming and that therefore a single Ga droplet per island site can be achieved.

Figures 3 (a) and (b) show histograms of the height

FIG. 2. AFM images with an array of 2.0 ML (a) single Ga droplets and (b) GaAs QDs under relatively lower energy laser irradiation (~ 12 mJ). Cross-sectional profiles of (c) single droplet and (d) QDs as marked by the dotted line in (a) and (b), respectively.

and width distributions for ordered GaAs QDs. It appears that the ordered dots have a mean h of 5.1 ± 0.6 nm and a mean D of 64.5 ± 8.6 nm. From further studies, we note that the size and the size distribution of the QDs depends on the T_s and deposition rate. With increasing T_s , the density of QDs increases resulting in multiple

QDs per patterning site, whilst the size of the QDs is reduced. Regions of the wafer outside of the interference spot do not show the nucleation of QDs and instead exhibit only 2D monolayer GaAs terraces. We are not able to form droplet QDs through conventional methods (without the laser pulse) using such a low deposition amount at the low temperatures we are using. We note typical Ga deposition amounts in the literature for the formation of QDs are $\sim 3\text{ML}$.^{18,19}

The observation of enhanced nucleation at pattern sites shows the effectiveness of shallow islands formed by the DLIP process. The benefits of the patterning process are therefore not just in terms of specific site localisation, but give an increased probability of droplet formation beyond that of spontaneous surface nucleation. The size distribution of our QDs appears relatively narrow compared to our observations of non-DLIP QDs (which show typically more than twice the height variation) but note that for the reasons discussed above, we do not have a direct comparison under the same growth conditions. We believe the size distribution of the ordered dots can be further improved by careful control of the island size and deposition amount.

FIG. 3. Histograms of the (a) height and (b) width distribution for the patterned GaAs QDs

The optical properties of the patterned QDs have been investigated by low-temperature PL spectroscopy. This requires AlGaAs capped samples. These are grown under similar low temperature conditions, but after crystallisation, the QDs were annealed at T_s of 400 °C for 10 min under an As_4 flux without capping to improve the optical quality of the QDs.²⁰ The QDs were then covered with a 10 nm $\text{Al}_{0.3}\text{Ga}_{0.7}\text{As}$ at 400 °C to prevent the two-dimensional regrowth of GaAs microcrystals. Then, the T_s was raised to a more optimum temperature for the AlGaAs of 630 °C and a further 90 nm barrier and final 10 nm GaAs cap layer were grown. Finally, to improve the overall crystal quality, we kept the sample at $T_s = 750$ °C for 30 min after growth with an arsenic flux supply.

PL spectra of the sample were taken using a 522 quasi-CW laser. The maximum incident power on the sample was 360 μW , but this could be reduced further by means of neutral density filters. The system used a $\times 100$ objective to collect the PL which has a laser spot

size of approximately 2 μm . The PL signal was collected by a fiber and fed to a high-resolution compact spectrometer which has a cooled Si CMOS detector array (ASEQ instruments).

Figure 4 shows excitation power-dependent PL spectra of GaAs QDs taken with a 15 K closed-cycle cryostat. The actual sample temperature was measured as 40 K from the GaAs bandgap temperature variation. The spectra have been scaled by dividing the PL intensity by the relative excitation intensity. The data shows a low temperature PL emission band which exhibits an unusually strong blue shift with excitation intensity. The intensity is increasing more than that given by the increase in the excitation intensity. The origins of this behaviour are not completely clear, however, the separation of the ground and excited states in this QD system is extremely small, with calculations using Nextnano³ suggesting only 15 meV separation between ground and first excited state. We therefore suggest that we may simply be seeing ground state saturation due to the relatively low QD density and that the higher order states which emerge cannot be fully resolved due to their small energy separation. The full width at half maximum of PL peak at low excitation intensity is approximately 34 meV. This is a positive result when compared to values of GaAs QD arrays fabricated by different site control techniques.^{15,23} As shown in the inset of Fig. 4, we observe QD emission at room temperature at 1.7 eV coupled with AlGaAs emission at 1.87 eV at room temperature. A further narrowing of the size distribution of GaAs QDs can be achieved by controlling the growth parameters further, such as the deposition rate and T_s for the formation of Ga droplets.¹⁹ Further improvements may come from employing the migration enhanced epitaxy method for the growth of the low temperature AlGaAs capping

FIG. 4. Excitation power-dependent PL spectra of ordered GaAs QDs at 40 K. The inset shows the PL spectrum at room temperature at a laser power $P = 360$ μW .

layer. There are reports that using this method the optical properties including linewidth can be further improved.^{21,22} Compared with our previous work on InAs/GaAs SK-QDs, in which DLIP was performed at T_s of 530 °C, in the case of the DE method the initial islands and Ga droplets are formed at much lower temperature ($T_s = 100$ °C) without arsenic flux supply. The fact that these two rather different growth parameters result in a similar localisation of QDs at pattern sites is a remarkable observation which shows the high efficiency of in-situ patterning with light pulses as a mechanism to nucleate nanostructures at specific sites.

In conclusion, we have investigated the growth of ordered GaAs/AlGaAs QDs by DE using in-situ DLIP. We are able to observe a precisely ordered array of Ga droplets which crystallise into single dots according to our imposed interference pattern, which has a period of 300 nm and results in a density of 8×10^8 cm⁻². In the AFM analysis, we find that the patterned QDs have an average h of 5.1 ± 0.6 nm and an average D of 64.5 ± 8.6 nm. The QD arrays show the clear low temperature PL emission at around 1.75 eV, which exhibits a strong blue shift with excitation intensity due to band filling. The emission linewidth is comparable with the best of the literature, but there is considerable room for further improvement of the QD size distribution. It will be necessary to further optimise the parameters for droplet formation in order to fabricate optimised high-quality GaAs/AlGaAs QD arrays by DLIP.

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Data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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